

TENSILE PROPERTIES OF CARBON NANOTUBE/EPOXY COMPOSITE FABRICATED BY PULTRUSION OF CARBON NANOTUBE SPUN YARN

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ABSTRACT

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) possess excellent mechanical properties; thus, CNTs may have great potential for use with reinforcing polymer resin. A large amount of research has been performed on CNT-reinforced polymers. However, the challenge lies in simultaneously achieving a sufficiently high volume fraction and the preferred alignment of long carbon nanotubes in order to take advantage of the excellent mechanical properties of each CNT. Recently, CNT spinning techniques using long CNTs for producing CNT spun yarns have been developed. CNT spun yarns have higher nanotube packing fractions and better fiber alignment in spite of using long CNTs. These characteristics are ideal for the preform when fabricating high-performance composite materials. To date, few studies have been published on epoxy-based composites using spun yarns, even though epoxy is widely used for the matrix of advance composite materials. In this study, epoxy-based composites were fabricated with a bundle of single-ply spun yarns as a preform using the pultrusion technique. Pultrusion is a continuous process for manufacturing composite columns and strips with longitudinal reinforcement. This paper demonstrates that pultrusion using CNT yarns enables us to fabricate quasi-unidirectionally reinforced CNT/epoxy composites with long CNT length and high volume fraction. In the curing period of the epoxy resin, a tensile force was applied in order to investigate its effect because the spun yarn contracts in the radial direction and stretches in the axial direction due to its twisted geometry, which may increase the volume fraction and improve fiber alignment. The tensile properties of the composites were explored by using quasi-static tensile tests.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) possess excellent mechanical properties, including a high modulus of about 1 TPa, a high tensile strength of more than 10 GPa, and a low density of 2.1 g/cm³. Thus, CNTs may have great potential for use with reinforcing polymer resin. A large amount of research has been performed on CNT-reinforced polymers [1-4]. However, the challenge lies in simultaneously achieving a sufficiently high volume fraction and the preferred alignment of long carbon nanotubes in order to take advantage of the excellent mechanical properties of each CNT [3]. Recently, CNT spinning techniques using long CNTs for producing CNT spun yarns have been developed [5-11]. CNT spun yarns have higher nanotube packing fractions and better fiber alignment in spite of using long CNTs. These characteristics are ideal for the preform when fabricating high-performance

composite materials [12-17]. To date, few studies have been published on epoxy-based composites using spun yarns [14, 18, 19], even though epoxy is widely used for the matrix of advance composite materials.

In this study, epoxy-based composites were fabricated with a bundle of single-ply spun yarns as a preform using the pultrusion technique [20]. Pultrusion is a continuous process for manufacturing composite columns and strips with longitudinal reinforcement. This paper demonstrates that pultrusion using CNT yarns enables us to fabricate quasi-unidirectionally reinforced CNT/epoxy composites with long CNT length and high volume fraction. In the curing period of the epoxy resin, a tensile force was applied in order to investigate its effect because the spun yarn contracts in the radial direction and stretches in the axial direction due to its twisted geometry [21], which may increase the volume fraction and improve fiber alignment. The tensile properties of the composites were explored by using quasi-static tensile tests.

2 MATERIALS AND SPECIMENS

MWNTs were vertically grown on a quartz glass plate with chemical vapor deposition using C_2H_2 and $FeCl_2$ as the base material and the catalyst, respectively [22]. Vertically aligned MWNTs on a substrate are called an MWNT array. The length and diameter of each carbon nanotube was about 1 mm and 50 nm, respectively. Spun yarns of MWNTs can be directly drawn from an MWNT array by using the dry-spinning technique. Figure 1 shows a schematic of the dry-spinning process of an MWNT spun yarn. Note that neither a chemical binder nor a surface treatment for the carbon nanotubes is required for dry spinning. More detail on the dry-spinning technique can be found in Ref. [10]. Figure 2 shows an SEM image of an MWNT spun yarn. Spun yarns were drawn at a rate of 100 mm/s with 30,000 rpm of spindle speed. The yarn diameter was about 45 μm . The twist angle, which was defined as the angle between the yarn axis and the outermost fiber direction, was 27–35°. The density was 0.55g/cm³, and the porosity of the spun yarn was about 70%. No surface treatments were performed on the spun yarns. Bisphenol-A type epoxy (Z2/H07, Nisshin Resin) was used in this study. The viscosity of the epoxy resin/hardener mixture was 300–500 mPa·s. The curing time of the epoxy was 72 h at room temperature.

Figure 1: Schematic of fabricating CNT spun yarn.

Figure 2: CNT spun yarn.

Tensile test specimens were prepared by using the pultrusion technique. A bundle of seven as-spun single-ply yarns was soaked in epoxy resin, and then the bundle was pultruded through a circular die with a diameter of about 120 μm . Finally, the pultruded bundle was cured under a constant tensile force at room temperature in air. In order to investigate the effect of the tensile force on the mechanical properties, the tensile force was changed from 0.1–0.3 N. A typical cross section and a magnified view of the cross section of a composite specimen are shown in Figure 3. The cross section was polished by using an argon ion beam polisher (IB-09010CP, JEOL). Note that gaps between yarns as well as a splitting of one yarn in Figure 3(a) were cracks caused by preliminary polishing for sample preparation. Though small voids in the order of a few μm were observed between and inside yarns, almost full impregnation of epoxy resin into yarns were achieved. Most specimens had resin rich region around the bundle of yarns. In this study, the cross-sectional area was defined as the area including the resin rich region. The densities of the cured specimens were 1.30–1.35 g/cm^3 .

Figure 3: Cross-section of a composite specimen.

3 RESULTS

Tensile tests of as-spun yarns and composite specimens were conducted in order to measure their tensile properties. The gauge length was 15 mm. The tensile tests were conducted at 1 mm/min of cross head speed, and the elongation of the gauge length was measured by a non-contact extensometer. There were a total of 25 as-spun yarn specimens, and there were four or five composite specimens for each volume fraction.

Typical stress–strain curves are shown in Figure 4. The stress–strain behavior of the as-spun yarn was nonlinear, and the average tensile strength was 175 MPa. On the other hand, the stress–strain behavior of composite specimens was almost linear, and the average tensile strength was higher than 200 MPa. In contrast to the earlier findings using single-ply yarns [18], the rule of mixtures using the mechanical properties of the as-spun yarn and epoxy resin does not hold; our experimental results strongly imply that the composite specimens were reinforced by each of the carbon nanotubes, not the spun yarns. The Young's modulus and tensile strength are plotted as a function of the fiber volume fraction in Figure 5, where the Young's modulus of the as-spun yarns and the composite specimens was defined as the slope between $\varepsilon = 0.25\%$ and 0.5% , and that of the epoxy resin was defined as the slope between $\varepsilon = 0.05\%$ and 0.25% .

Both the Young's modulus and tensile strength significantly increased with increasing volume fraction. The Young's modulus and tensile strength at $V_f = 25.5\%$ were 15 times and 7 times as high as those of the epoxy resin, respectively. The failure strain ranged from 0.52% to 1.04%, which are almost the same as the failure strains in Ref. [18, 19].

Figure 4: Typical stress-strain curves.

Figure 5: Mechanical properties vs. Fiber volume fraction.

9 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, MWNT-reinforced epoxy with a higher volume fraction and better alignment was pultruded by using as-spun single-ply yarn preforms whose MWNT length was 1 mm long. Epoxy resin was well impregnated into the preforms, resulting in sufficient load transfer from the resin to the carbon nanotubes. The composites had excellent mechanical properties, exceeding high-strength aluminum alloys in their specific modulus and specific strength.

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